

Менеджмент

УДК 658.012.4:658.15

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17214472>

**Методологічні підходи до управління стратегічними змінами та
прийняття інвестиційних рішень в операційній діяльності сучасних
організацій**

Дідур Ганна Іванівна

кандидат економічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри менеджменту,

Одеський державний аграрний університет, м. Одеса, Україна,

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9450-3124>

Scopus Author ID: 57992068400

Researcher ID: JOV-6639-2023

Запша Галина Миколаївна

доктор економічних наук, професор, завідувач кафедри менеджменту,

Одеський державний аграрний університет, м. Одеса, Україна

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2657-9367>

Scopus Author ID: 59007462900

Researcher ID: AAP-3837-2020

Телічко Наталія Александрівна

кандидат економічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри менеджменту,

Одеський державний аграрний університет, м. Одеса, Україна

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1571-3364>

Scopus Author ID: 57201722250

Researcher ID: ABB-1244-2021

Мельничук Оксана Іванівна

кандидат економічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри менеджменту,
Одеський державний аграрний університет, м. Одеса, Україна
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2616-0478>

Кравцова Олександра Олегівна
здобувачка освітнього ступеню магістр
Одеський державний аграрний університет, м. Одеса, Україна
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5046-8396>

Прийнято: 14.09.2025 | Опубліковано: 27.09.2025

Анотація: У статті розглянуто методологічні підходи до управління стратегічними змінами та прийняття інвестиційних рішень в операційній діяльності сучасних організацій. Актуальність дослідження зумовлена зростаючою складністю бізнес-середовища, впливом глобалізації, цифрової трансформації та воєнних викликів, що потребує інтегрованих підходів до забезпечення стійкості та конкурентоспроможності підприємств. **Метою** статті є теоретичне обґрунтування та розвиток методологічних основ управління стратегічними змінами та прийняття інвестиційних рішень з урахуванням динаміки зовнішнього середовища. **Методологія** дослідження базується на використанні системного підходу, що дозволяє комплексно розглядати управління стратегічними змінами та прийняття інвестиційних рішень у взаємозв'язку з внутрішніми та зовнішніми факторами розвитку організації. Структурно-функціональний підхід використано для ідентифікації ключових підсистем управління змінами та визначення їх функцій. **Результати.** У результаті визначено сутність стратегічних змін як організаційних трансформацій, що забезпечують довгостроковий розвиток підприємства, та обґрунтовано їх тісний зв'язок із прийняттям інвестиційних рішень. Розроблено структурну модель системи управління стратегічними змінами, яка включає

цільову, аналітичну, планову, організаційну, ресурсну, виконавчу та контрольну підсистеми. Систематизовано функції управління змінами (планування, організація, координація, мотивація та контроль), що інтегрують стратегічні та інвестиційні аспекти розвитку. Виокремлено ключові етапи процесу - підготовчий, впровадження, контроль та оцінку ефективності, - які забезпечують цілісність стратегічних трансформацій. **Висновки.** У висновках наголошено на необхідності використання комплексного методологічного підходу, що поєднує системний, процесний та ситуаційний рівні аналізу, а також підкреслено значення подолання опору персоналу змінам і формування культури інновацій. Подальші дослідження доцільно зосередити на розвитку компетенцій працівників для підвищення ефективності управління стратегічними змінами та інвестиційними проєктами.

Ключові слова: методологія менеджменту, концепція стратегічного управління, функції управління, етапи впровадження змін, опір змінам.

Methodological approaches to managing strategic changes and investment decisions in the operational activities of modern organizations

Hanna Didur

PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Department of Management,

Odesa State Agrarian University, Ukraine, Odesa

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9450-3124>

Scopus Author ID: 57992068400

Researcher ID: JOV-6639-2023

Halyna Zapsha

Dr. Sc. (Ekon), Professor, Head of the Department of Management, Professor,

Odesa State Agrarian University, Ukraine, Odesa

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2657-9367>

Scopus Author ID: 59007462900

Researcher ID: AAP-3837-2020

Nataliia Telichko

PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Department of Management,

Odesa State Agrarian University, Ukraine, Odesa

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1571-3364>

Scopus Author ID: 57201722250

Researcher ID: ABB-1244-2021

Oksana Melnychuk

PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Department of Management,

Odesa State Agrarian University, Ukraine, Odesa

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2616-0478>

Oleksandra Kravtsova

Master's degree applicant

Odesa State Agrarian University, Ukraine, Odesa

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5046-8396>

Abstract: The purpose of the article is to provide a theoretical justification and to develop methodological foundations for managing strategic changes and making investment decisions, taking into account the dynamics of the external environment. **The research methodology** is based on a systematic approach, which makes it possible to comprehensively consider strategic change management and investment decision-making in relation to internal and external factors of organisational development. A structural-functional approach is applied to identify key change management subsystems and to determine their functions. **Results.** The study defines the essence of strategic changes as organisational transformations that ensure the long-

term development of the enterprise and substantiates their close connection with investment decision-making. A structural model of the strategic change management system has been developed, encompassing target, analytical, planning, organisational, resource, executive, and control subsystems. The study systematises the functions of change management (planning, organisation, coordination, motivation, and control), which integrate strategic and investment aspects of development. The key stages of the process – preparation, implementation, control, and evaluation of effectiveness – are identified as ensuring the integrity of strategic transformations. **Conclusions.** The conclusions highlight the need for a comprehensive methodological approach that integrates systemic, process, and situational levels of analysis, as well as the importance of overcoming staff resistance to change and fostering an innovation-oriented culture. Further research should be directed at developing employee competencies to enhance the effectiveness of strategic change and investment project management.

Keywords: management methodology, strategic management concept, management functions, stages of change implementation, resistance to change.

Problem statement. Effective management of strategic changes and sound investment decisions within the framework of an organisation's operational activities are key to ensuring its long-term sustainable economic development. In academic discourse, the categories of 'change management', 'investment decisions', and 'operational activities' are considered interrelated and integrated into the strategic management system. The management methodology determines the logic of building mechanisms for the organisation's adaptation to transformations in its internal and external environments and also forms the basis for the development of tools that serve as a basis for management and investment decision-making.

The development and implementation of strategic changes involve applying a range of scientific approaches, such as systemic, process-based, situational, innovative, and behavioural approaches. Each of them provides a different interpretation of the

relationship between operational activities, strategic goals, and investment programmes. The systemic approach focuses on the complexity of changes; the process approach, on their gradual implementation; the situational approach, on flexible responses to uncertainty; and the innovative approach, on the integration of new technologies and the digitalisation of business processes.

In light of current challenges such as globalisation, digital transformation, martial law, logistics issues, increasing competition, and evolving consumer preferences, the need to enhance the methodology for managing strategic changes and investment decisions is becoming increasingly pertinent. This requires an in-depth analysis of existing theoretical concepts, the adaptation of global strategic management models for national use, and the development of new, science-based approaches to improving organisational operational efficiency.

Therefore, the relevance of this study lies in the need to establish a modern methodological basis for managing strategic changes and investment decisions.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Recent research highlights a shift towards integrated, multi-criteria, and adaptive methodologies in strategic change management and investment decision-making. The literature emphasises the need for approaches that balance financial analysis with strategic, organisational, and contextual factors in order to improve decision quality and organisational resilience.

Strategic change management increasingly relies on cognitive modelling, scenario modelling, and systems thinking to formalise and forecast the impact of change initiatives. When applied in open innovation systems, cognitive models help organisations anticipate the effects of strategic changes on resource allocation and performance outcomes, supporting more informed and adaptive decision-making [1]. Scenario modelling and structural balance algorithms are also employed to diagnose financial prerequisites and optimise resource use, thereby improving the effectiveness of change management strategies [2].

Recent studies emphasise the importance of combining strategic management tools with financial analytics to develop robust investment strategies [3,4]. This

integration enables organisations to align investment decisions with broader strategic objectives, adapt to environmental changes, and manage operational risks more effectively [3,4,5]. Participatory processes and expert input further enhance transparency and the alignment of stakeholder interests in the decision-making process [6].

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite significant achievements in the field of strategic change management and investment decision-making, several important aspects remain under-researched. First, there is limited attention to integrating strategic changes in operational activities with investment decision-making processes, particularly in a highly dynamic external environment. Second, approaches to overcoming organisational resistance to change in the context of implementing investment strategies remain underdeveloped. This is largely due to the complexity arising from the interplay of financial, organisational, and behavioural factors, as well as the lack of unified tools that enable effective coordination of strategic transformations with the investment priorities of enterprises. Addressing these aspects is essential for enhancing organisational sustainability and adaptability.

Formulation of the article's objectives (task statement). The objective of the article is to provide a theoretical justification and to develop methodological approaches to managing strategic changes and making investment decisions within the operational activities of modern organisations. This takes into account the dynamics of the external environment and the need to ensure long-term competitiveness.

In accordance with this objective, the following tasks have been identified:

- to analyse contemporary scientific approaches to managing strategic changes and making investment decisions in the operational activities of organisations;
- to systematise the methodological foundations for combining strategic change management and investment decision-making processes;
- to substantiate the feasibility of applying integrated methodological approaches to ensure the effectiveness of operational activities.

Presentation of the main research material. Strategic changes are organisational changes that occur within the framework of strategic management. These changes form the core of any strategy, as they transform the organisation into a qualitatively new strategic state [7, 8].

The modern understanding of strategic management is the result of an evolutionary process. The development of strategic management concepts was driven by changes in economic, technological, and social conditions affecting business operations, as well as by increasingly sophisticated methods used to manage industrial organisations. As the economic environment in which enterprises operated grew increasingly complex and unpredictable, management systems also became more sophisticated, while the conceptual understanding of strategic management continued to evolve.

It should be noted that the emergence of a new understanding of strategic management did not render the previous one obsolete. On the contrary, each subsequent concept incorporates the best features of the previous one. Alongside the development of strategic management concepts, the concept of strategy itself has also evolved.

Contemporary researchers define strategic management as a dynamic, theory-driven, and multi-paradigmatic management activity focusing on how organisations can achieve and sustain competitive advantage in a rapidly changing environment. It integrates a variety of theoretical perspectives, including resource-based, industrial organisation, and knowledge-based views, and employs both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to address complex real-world strategic problems [9,10,11].

Strategic management centres on formulating, implementing, and evaluating actions that enable organisations to achieve long-term objectives and maintain superior performance, often in the face of uncertainty and global competition [11,12]. The field draws on economics, sociology, political science, and cognitive science, reflecting its pluralistic and evolving nature. This diversity enables the integration of multiple frameworks to explain organisational behaviour and performance [10,13].

Modern strategic management research emphasises empirical rigour and practical relevance, aiming to bridge the gap between academic theory and managerial practice. Researchers stress the need for strategic management to address challenges such as globalisation, digitalisation, and technological disruption, which require the continuous adaptation of strategies and methodologies [14,15,16].

A strategic vision is a formal framework that guides managerial decision-making regarding the organisation's long-term prospects.

When developing a change strategy or making investment decisions, the management team must consider:

- how the company's future is envisaged;
- the direction in which the company should develop;
- the future technologies, products, and customers the company will have;
- the long-term market positions the company aims to occupy.

Strategic change management can therefore be defined as a set of principles, methods, tools, and systematic measures employed by management to influence economic activity and facilitate strategic changes that determine an organisation's long-term development. The purpose of these measures is to transition the enterprise from its current state to a desired state, in accordance with strategic goals that take into account stakeholder requirements and the influence of the external environment in which the organisation operates.

Strategic change management and investment decision-making are intricately linked processes that serve as the backbone of organisational development. When integrated, they form a unified and effective decision-making system that emphasises long-term operational efficiency by merging strategic management principles with rigorous investment analysis techniques.

Within an organisation, strategic changes encompass comprehensive transformations that may affect business processes, organisational structures, and corporate cultures, each aimed at achieving specific strategic objectives. For instance, an organisation may need to overhaul its supply chain management processes or

reshape its corporate culture to foster innovation and collaboration. Correspondingly, investment decisions play a crucial role in providing the essential resources—financial capital, physical assets, technical tools, and advanced technologies—required to support these transformative changes. It is therefore critical for investment policy to align with the overarching strategy for change.

The implementation of strategic changes and the effective utilisation of investment resources occur during the organisation's operational activities. For example, adopting advanced production technologies or enhancing logistics capabilities may require substantial investment in state-of-the-art equipment, specialised software solutions, and comprehensive staff training programmes. Furthermore, the outcomes of these operational activities directly influence the success and effectiveness of the investment decisions made.

To navigate the complex landscape of strategic change management, organisations must apply comprehensive methodological approaches:

- a systematic approach, which views strategic change and investment decisions as interdependent components of an integrated management system. It recognises that decisions in one area can significantly affect another, leading to a more coherent strategy;
- a process approach, in which integration is achieved through careful synchronisation of the planning, implementation, and monitoring phases of both change initiatives and investment projects. This ensures consistency across phases and keeps stakeholders informed and engaged throughout the process;
- a situational approach, which acknowledges that investment decisions are shaped by the unique characteristics of the strategic changes being implemented and the external environment in which the organisation operates. Market conditions, competition, and regulatory requirements, for instance, may influence the nature and timing of investment decisions.

A thoughtfully organised integration of these elements fosters synergy within the organisation, allowing investments to support not only the current operational

framework but also to drive sustainable, long-term strategic changes. This holistic approach ultimately empowers the organisation, leading to enhanced operational efficiency, improved competitive positioning, and robust sustainable development.

To implement this approach, a management system must be established that combines the main components in a structured way and ensures their coordinated interaction. The strategic change management system comprises interrelated elements, each performing a specific function to ensure the effectiveness of the organisation's operational activities (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Components of the system for managing strategic changes in the operational activities of an enterprise

Source: compiled by the authors

The system designed to manage strategic changes consists of a series of interconnected subsystems, each playing a crucial role in ensuring the effectiveness and integrity of the organisation's strategic development process.

The target subsystem defines long-term strategic guidelines and investment priorities, forming the foundation for managerial decisions. The analytical subsystem assesses internal resources, potential risks, and external market conditions, providing justification for strategic changes and investment decisions. The planning subsystem develops scenarios, programmes, and projects that anticipate future challenges and opportunities. Meanwhile, the organisational subsystem establishes structures, coordination mechanisms, and accountability. The resource subsystem ensures the effective accumulation, allocation, and optimisation of financial, material, and human

resources in line with strategic priorities. The implementation subsystem translates plans into operational actions that emphasise innovation and technological advancement. The control subsystem provides continuous feedback through monitoring and evaluation, enabling timely adjustments and ensuring alignment with organisational objectives.

Together, these interconnected subsystems form a robust and integrated framework that enhances the organisation's adaptability in a rapidly changing environment. This framework significantly contributes to long-term competitiveness and sustainable development, positioning the enterprise for future success.

Strategic change management functions reflect the process of implementing activities that introduce changes to operational practices. These functions form the basis of a self-organising change management system and must be integrated into the enterprise's overall strategic management framework. Implementation occurs through functions such as planning, organising, coordinating, motivating, and controlling. However, in the context of strategic changes aimed at innovative development, the composition of general management functions is determined by the nature of the changes and the specifics of the change process (see Table 1).

These strategic change management functions represent the fundamental areas of an organisation's operations and are designed to ensure the alignment of objectives, resources, and outcomes. Their successful implementation, however, requires a systematic and sequential approach. Consequently, it is essential to delineate the stages of strategic change management within operational activities, as these stages establish the sequence of practical actions and safeguard the coherence of strategic transformations in contemporary organisations.

Table 1

Functions of managing strategic changes in the organization's operations

Change management function	Content of strategic change management functions
Planning	drawing up a plan for change as part of the company's strategic planning system, using modern approaches to planning and implementing change; identifying priority areas for investment; forming an investment portfolio and allocating resources in line with expected results; developing a programme for implementing the planned strategic changes
Organization	form working teams and establish their internal structure to implement strategic changes; empowering these teams and their members with the appropriate powers, functions and responsibilities. effective coordination between structural units and working teams must be ensured. developing interaction and communication mechanisms to ensure coordinated investment decisions. creating an organisational culture that supports strategic change and innovation.
Coordination	developing procedural decisions and coordinating actions to implement strategic changes. establishing feedback procedures. ensuring that investment decisions are consistent with the organisation's overall development strategy. establishing mechanisms for cross-functional interaction between departments and working teams. synchronising timelines and resources when implementing strategic changes and investment projects.
Motivation	motivating work teams to implement changes to economic activity effectively; motivating employees to minimise their resistance to change; developing a system of material and non-material incentives that are linked to achieving strategic goals and implementing investment projects; creating a corporate culture that supports innovation, strategic change and the ability to make new management decisions.
Control	ongoing monitoring of changes being implemented; monitoring the results and effectiveness of strategic changes; assessing the feasibility and effectiveness of investment decisions; devising corrective management measures in response to deviations from planned indicators; developing a reporting system to ensure transparency of the results of strategic changes for management and stakeholders.

Source: compiled by the authors

Accordingly, the following stages of managing strategic changes in business activities are proposed (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Stages of managing strategic changes in operational activities

Source: developed by the authors based on [17]

During the preparation stage, change management in business activities should be considered from two perspectives: tactical and strategic. From a tactical perspective, change management involves the ability to implement changes in a timely manner, achieve set objectives, reduce resistance to change, and enhance employee adaptability. From a strategic perspective, change management entails integrating continuous changes into management practices so that they become familiar and expected for all employees, while their temporary absence may induce stress and uncertainty. The effective implementation of a change management strategy contributes significantly to the organisation's competitiveness.

The preparatory stage also involves determining the number of personnel involved in implementing strategic changes in operational activities and investment decisions, as well as defining the strategy, timing, and necessary resources, including external consultants and experts. At this stage, resistance to change is inevitable. Given its multifaceted nature, appropriate prevention methods and countermeasures must be established.

The implementation stage of strategic changes in operational activities encompasses the execution of planned changes and involves complex procedures aimed at realising investment decisions and organisational modifications. The approach to implementation may depend on several factors, including the speed of

change execution, the effectiveness of managerial oversight, the utilisation of external mechanisms such as consulting services, and whether the focus is centralised or localised.

Successful implementation of strategic changes depends on several key aspects: effective communication with team members in line with the chosen change strategy; active involvement of employees in investment decisions and change processes to foster a sense of ownership; a detailed implementation plan; and the availability of necessary financial, material, and human resources.

A mandatory stage in managing strategic changes is monitoring the implementation process and evaluating the effectiveness of investment decisions. Control points and measures should be developed in accordance with the chosen change management strategy. Critical factors for effective control include the availability of responsible personnel, allocation of sufficient time, and the competency level of staff. Additional measures may include training personnel in modern investment decision-making methods, effective change management techniques, and task delegation during monitoring.

The final stage involves analysing the effectiveness of implemented changes and adjusting the change management process accordingly. This step is essential for developing an action plan that supports strategic changes and corrects unsatisfactory outcomes. Evaluation requires: analysing achieved results versus set goals, identifying obstacles and how they were overcome, obtaining feedback from stakeholders and the target audience, and reporting on outcomes. Conducting a qualitative assessment of the process and results can reduce future implementation risks and enhance organisational learning.

Considering the above characteristics of the stages of strategic change management, it can be concluded that successful implementation requires leaders with the necessary knowledge and skills. By addressing all these factors, effective strategic changes can be consistently achieved.

One of the most challenging aspects of managing strategic changes and implementing investment decisions is employee resistance to innovation. This resistance often manifests not as overt opposition, but as a natural reaction to loss of stability or uncertainty. Its intensity depends on employees' value orientations: some prioritise security, while others focus on professional development and career growth. Consequently, organisations must develop a comprehensive system of measures to minimise resistance, increase motivation, and facilitate employee adaptation. This includes optimising organisational structures, providing effective feedback and information support for strategic decisions, and offering training and education to enhance employee qualifications. Particular attention should be given to integrating motivation and adaptation mechanisms with the enterprise's investment priorities, as the human factor ultimately determines the success of strategic changes and the achievement of expected returns on investment projects.

Conclusions. Research on strategic changes as an object of management, viewed through the lens of modern theoretical concepts, allows them to be defined as organisational transformations that occur within the context of strategic management.

Based on a synthesis of scholars' approaches to the concept of strategic management, the essence of managing strategic changes in enterprises' economic activities can be understood as a set of systematic measures undertaken by organisational management to influence the enterprise as a platform for strategic transformation.

In the management of strategic changes and investment decision-making, a comprehensive methodological approach is proposed, incorporating systemic, process, and situational approaches. The integration of these approaches promotes organisational synergy, enabling investments to support not only the current operational structure but also to contribute to sustainable, long-term strategic transformations.

The article examines contemporary tools for developing and implementing strategic changes and investment decisions in enterprise operations. Key aspects

highlighted include the components of the strategic change management system, strategic change management functions, stages of strategic change implementation, and measures to overcome resistance to change. Employee resistance is identified as a critical factor in human resource management within the context of implementing strategic changes and investment decisions.

Strategic changes and the adoption and execution of investment decisions are closely tied to employee involvement and cannot be effectively implemented without it. Therefore, further research should focus on developing programmes to enhance systematic thinking, business vision, independent decision-making, leadership, teamwork, effective communication, and stress management. Such universal training equips employees to embrace change and overcome resistance, thereby ensuring the successful implementation of strategic initiatives.

References:

1. Bartosova V., Drobyazko S., Bielialov T., Nechyporuk L., Dzhyhora O.. Company strategic change management in the open innovation system. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*. 2023. Vol.10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100087>
2. Смерічевський С. Ф., Ареф'єва О. В., Пілецька С. Т. Формування стратегічних рішень при управлінні змінами на підприємстві. *Бізнес Інформ*. 2022. №6. С. 109-117. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32983/2222-4459-2022-6-108-117>
3. Степанова А. Методичне забезпечення формування інвестиційної стратегії підприємства. *Формування ринкової економіки в Україні*. 2023. Вип. 49. С. 78-86. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.30970/meu.2023.49.0.4908>
4. Ochuba N., Amoo O., Okafor E., Usman F., Akinrinola O. Conceptual Development and Financial Analytics for Strategic Decision-Making in Telecommunications, Focusing on Assessing Investment Opportunities and Managing Risks in Satellite Projects. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*. 2024. Vol. 6. P. 594-607 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51594/ijmer.v6i3.847>

5. Alkaraan F. Strategic Investment Decision-Making Perspectives. *Advances in Strategic Management*. 2015. Vol. 14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-361X20150000014004>
6. Barbieri G., Vega A., Gutierrez J., Laserna J., Mateus L. Strategic Capital Investments in Asset Management: A Value-Based Approach. *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering*. 2025. Vol. 31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/jqme-11-2023-0104>
7. Занора В. О., Бут А. О., Матухно Ю. С. Стратегічне управління розвитком та управління стратегічними змінами на підприємстві. *Економіка та суспільство*. 2021. Вип. 32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2021-32-81>
8. Полінкевич О. М., Волинець І. Г. Управління стратегічними змінами та інноваціями на підприємстві: навч. посіб. Луцьк, 2018. 352 с.
9. Таран-Лала О., Сухорук К. Особливості стратегічного управління підприємством. *Економіка та суспільство*. 2021. № 25. <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2021-25-66>
10. Ferreira J., Fernandes C., Ratten V. A Co-Citation Bibliometric Analysis of Strategic Management Research. *Scientometrics*. 2016. Vol. 109. P. 1–32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2008-0>
11. Guerras-Martín L., Madhok A., Montoro-Sánchez Á. The Evolution of Strategic Management Research: Recent Trends and Current Directions. *Business Research Quarterly*. 2014. Vol. 17. P. 69–76. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brq.2014.03.001>
12. Ситницький М. В. Концепція стратегічного управління розвитком дослідницьких університетів. *Теоретичні та прикладні питання економіки. Збірник наукових праць*. 2021. Випуск 1 (42). С. 40-48. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17721/tppe.2021.42.4>
13. Hou T., Li J. Conceptual Underpinnings: Theory Selection in Strategic Management Research. *Management Decision*. 2024. Vol. 62. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-08-2023-1423>

14. Graebner M., Knott A., Lieberman M., Mitchell W. Empirical Inquiry Without Hypotheses: A Question-Driven, Phenomenon-Based Approach to Strategic Management Research. *Strategic Management Journal*. 2022. Vol. 44. P. 3-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3393>
15. White G., Guldiken O., Hemphill T., He W., Khoobdeh M. Trends in International Strategic Management Research From 2000 to 2013: Text Mining and Bibliometric Analyses. *Management International Review*. 2016. Vol. 56. P. 35-65. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11575-015-0260-9>
16. Ляхович Л. Стратегічна поведінка компаній в умовах війни та повоєнного відновлення. *Економічний простір*. 2022. №1. С. 139-143.
17. Дідур Г., Довган В., Пирожок Є. Особливості управління стратегічними змінами господарської діяльності сучасних організацій. *Економічний вісник Причорномор'я*. 2024. №5. С. 21-32.